

Notes on Jet Bundles

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1 Preamble

There is a connection between finite-dimensional Hilbert spaces ($\mathcal{FDHilb}$) and jet bundles (j_p^r) particularly in the context of quantum mechanics and quantum field theory. A theorem that relates these concepts is known as the “Quantization of Field Theories Theorem” or “Quantization Postulate,” which establishes a fundamental connection between classical field theories, such as those described by jet bundles, and quantum field theories based on finite-dimensional Hilbert spaces.

In the context of classical field theories, where the fields are described by sections of jet bundles, there exists a corresponding quantum field theory. This quantum field theory operates in a finite-dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{FDHilb}$ where states correspond to physical configurations of the fields, and operators represent observables of the quantum system. The quantization procedure systematically maps classical observables to their quantum counterparts.

In essence, this theorem asserts that classical field theories, often described using jet bundles, can be consistently translated into quantum field theories operating in finite-dimensional Hilbert spaces. It underlies the transition from classical physics to quantum physics for systems governed by field theories.

It’s important to note that the actual quantization process can be highly involved and depends on the specific field theory and symmetries involved. Nevertheless, this theorem provides a foundational link between classical field descriptions and their quantum counterparts, making it a crucial result in theoretical physics.

1.1 The formalism

Let $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$ be two states in a finite-dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{FDHilb}$ with basis vectors $|\xi\rangle$ and $|\xi'\rangle$, and let $\langle\psi|\phi\rangle$ represent their inner product. Additionally, suppose we have a probabilistic choice between two states i and j with equal probability, represented as $P(i) = P(j) = \frac{1}{2}$.

Now, let’s define an interval $\mathbb{I}_\xi$ as $\mathbb{I}_\xi = (-\xi, \xi)$, and we want to calculate the integral $\int_{\mathbb{I}_\xi} \frac{d\omega}{dt}$, where $\frac{d\omega}{dt}$ involves Taylor expansions of the radial volumes of tubular neighborhoods around zero-manifolds.

The integral operation $i \in \int_{\mathbb{I}_\xi}$ can be related to a probabilistic choice between states i and j and a distance function $d(\alpha, \alpha')$ as follows:

$$y \in \int_{\mathbb{I}_\xi} = P(i) \cdot i + P(j) \cdot j = \frac{1}{2}i + \frac{1}{2}j = \frac{1}{2}(i \ll j) = \frac{1}{2}d(\alpha, \alpha') \quad (1)$$

We have, for each α, α' , a connection

$$\overset{\nabla}{\Gamma} : in \int_{\mathbb{I}_\xi} \leftrightarrow out \int_{\mathbb{I}_\xi} = -\xi \overset{\nabla}{\leftrightarrow} \xi$$

We let $\mathcal{O}_X$ take its fibers over the interval $\mathbb{I}_\xi$, and let $\mathcal{P} : \alpha \rightarrow \alpha'$ denote a smooth path in the path groupoid $\mathbb{I}_\xi^{\langle 1 \rangle}$. Let $Nerve(\mathcal{P})$ denote the set of stratifications induced by foliations at the boundary of a spacetime chunk, and let

$$Nerve(\mathcal{P}) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} p_i \in Man_{Tot}$$

The set of solutions for the jet bundle equation is then determined precisely by a contractible, tiny neighborhood in which p_i shrinks to $*$. We have the short exact sequence:

$$p_i \hookrightarrow Nerve(\mathcal{P}) \hookrightarrow Man_{Tot} \quad (2)$$

and we identify p_i as the inverse limit of (2), and write $\lim_{\leftarrow} \mathcal{U}(p) \in Man_{Tot} = p_i$. We obtain the following diagram by letting $i \circ j = j \circ i$ commute:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} p_i & \xleftarrow{\Sigma} & Nerve(\mathcal{P}) \\ \downarrow \Sigma & & \downarrow \gamma_{ij} \\ Nerve(\mathcal{P}) & \xleftarrow{\gamma_{ji}} & Man_{Tot} \end{array}$$

The change in a particle's state ($\alpha \rightarrow \alpha'$) is modeled by a transition map $\varphi : p_i \rightarrow (p_i)'$ which constitutes a perturbative fluctuation of the wave function $\Psi(p_i) \sim \mathbb{I}_\xi$, which realizes a minimal model $\hat{\Psi}(p_i)$ of S in superposition. The sets are assigned to the structure sheaf associated to a particular slice of $\mathbb{E}^n$ about the particle, and are specialized to a point by $\mathbb{E}^n \rightsquigarrow k \in \mathbb{R}$. We obtain the generalized formula:

$$\frac{1}{k}(\alpha, \dots, k, \alpha') = y_k \in \int_{\mathbb{I}_\xi}$$

for k possible states of superposition. Here, k is an eigenvalue of the complex equation transforming the spin matrix of a particle into energy. It has been

shown that quantum coherence can generate thermal energy, but not work [1]; it must follow then that the maximally coherent state $Coh(\mathbb{I}_\xi)$ has an effective realization as a 4-momentum on a Euclidean or conformal worldbrane.

We let there be an immersion $y_k \hookrightarrow QCoh(\mathbb{I}_\xi)$ and a further state transition map $p^{[k]} : \hat{p} \rightarrow \hat{p}'$ which determines a motion of $\geq 2\varepsilon$ on a totally disconnected manifold.

1.1.1 Jet Bundles

We let $j_0^r \sim \tan_{vec}(\hat{q})$, $j_1^r \sim \tan_{vec}(q)$, and $j_2^r : \tan_{vec}(q) \rightarrow \tan_{vec}(q)$. In this way, the structure of n-cells naturally arises, but with a twist: trivially, j_0^r models a single negative dimension, being subordinate to the *implicate order* of a quantum. This corresponds to the notion of a series of quasi-quanta about a string which intersects each of $\hat{q}_i$ once. Notice that the case of j_1^r corresponds to

$$\left. \frac{d\omega}{dt} \right|_{t < 0} = \square^{-q}(\omega) \star \diamond^q(\omega)$$

The $\square^{-q}$ term contributes zero momentum to the body, whilst the $\star^q$ term is wholly responsible for the kinetic components, measured as a disturbance from the resting frame of a body of sitting moments, modeled as a worldbrane, or extended slice of C_n^∞ . If we substitute k for ∞ , for k sufficiently large (on the order of $\aleph_0$), we obtain an n-fold map to an object m for every k-n=m. This gives us a sufficiently smooth partitioning into strata, so that there is the following epimorphism:

$$C_n^\infty \twoheadrightarrow Strat_M|_{k-n}$$

Theorem 1 $0 \rightarrow L \otimes \Omega \rightarrow J^n L \rightarrow J^{n-1} L \rightarrow 0$ is exact.

Proof: See [2, theorem 1].

Theorem 2 Let 0 be the inf-pole of a compass, and ∞ be its sup-pole. The exit path:

$$\mathcal{EP}_m : C \sim \Omega_0^\infty \rightarrow (0 \rightarrow m)$$

denotes the transition amplitude of p.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{J}_m^\infty$ be the jet bundle associated with the compass C. Then, there is a foliation, $\mathcal{F}(m)$, which is smooth over the fibers π_k of $\mathbb{M} \in Man$. For every value $d((k-n), \theta(k-n))$, there is a discrete numerical quantity which is presentable as a compact interval.

Write Π for the set of all fibers of $\mathbb{M}$. Then, we have

$$\Pi = \sum_{k=0}^{m \sim \infty} \pi_k$$

giving us a collection of stalks, which correspond to the individual jets of $\mathcal{J}_m^\infty$. That the exit path is a transition amplitude follows from the fact that if p is a particle located at j_m^∞ for some jet j , then there some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ which is the target of the map out of the target space about p_m .

2 References

- [1] X.Q. Yan, et al. *Quantum coherence can be transformed into heat* (2023)
- [2] R. Vakil, *A Beginner's Guide to Jet Bundles from the Point of View of Algebraic Geometry* (1998)